

Glacial Motion

How can SAR detect glacial motion?

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In this StoryMap we will show how Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images can be used to detect glacial motion. The capabilities presented here are focused on L-band radars such as NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR Mission).

Background

Glaciers and snow in mountain regions are changing drastically in the 21st century, and Earth observations are crucial for quantifying how these changes impact water resources, sea level rise, and river ecosystems. NISAR can provide information about snow conditions and measure the flow of mountain glaciers over time, helping us better

understand the scope and impact of change. To find more information, check out these NISAR white papers ([Mountain Glaciers and Snow Hydrology](#), [Glaciers, Ice Sheets, and the Oceans](#))

Watch this video to learn about NASA's ongoing research on high mountain glaciers. Later in this StoryMap, you can explore case studies that showcase the use of radar data to map glacier movement in Alaska and Chile.

NASA Explorers: High Mountain Glaciers

Animation: How a Glaci...

Animation: How a Glacier Melts

This video describes the process of glacier melting in Greenland. During the summer, meltwater from the glacier forms rivers and pools that move through channels within the ice, eventually reaching the glacier bed below and flowing to the ocean.

How to map glacial motion with SAR?

There are multiple methods that can be employed to map patterns and magnitude of glacier movement with SAR.

One of the methods scientists use is interferometric SAR (InSAR). InSAR is a technique that calculates the difference between two SAR images of the same area, collected at different times. The figure below depicts a radar sensor transmitting microwave pulses and receiving backscatter echoes before and after a change in the reflected surface.

Interferograms are maps of surface change produced from InSAR data. To create interferograms, two SAR images are compared to determine if the ground shifted towards or away from the sensor between the two acquisitions. These ground shifts are reflected in the radar's signal and can be used to create a map of displacement, or interferogram. Glacial motion is reflected in the radar's signal and can be used to create a map of displacement, or interferogram.

Refer to the technology section at the end of this StoryMap to learn more about interpreting interferograms and fringes!

Other methods for tracking glacier movement are speckle or offset tracking. In speckle tracking, algorithms analyze the intensity of SAR images and identify patterns of "speckles" or pixels. By measuring the amount of shift in these speckle patterns between different scenes, SAR can be used to provide vector estimates of displacement. Similarly, offset tracking estimates the displacement of glacier features. InSAR is limited in cases of fast moving glaciers or high temporal separation between SAR images. In these cases, speckle or offset tracking can be employed.

Pixel tracking measures motion and an advance of ~20 meters from 2013 to 2014.

2013 (left) and 2014 (right)

Case Studies

Alaska Glaciers

In a study conducted by Burgess et al. in 2013, researchers utilized SAR satellite images of glaciers taken at different times to determine the movement of ice. The Japanese Space Agency's PALSAR satellite was used in this study, operated in the L-band wavelength like NISAR. The researchers employed a method called offset tracking, which involved comparing the satellite images of glaciers and identifying corresponding features. By examining areas of the landscape that remained stationary and measuring the displacement between the two images, they were able to calculate ice movement and provide an estimate of the ice velocity.

Surface velocity map of the Wrangell and St Elias Ranges. Source: Burgess et. al 2013, <https://www.nature.com/articles/ncomms3146>

Monitoring glacier velocity helps researchers understand the factors driving changes in glaciers. For example, by quantifying the rate at which ice calves into the ocean from glaciers, it becomes possible to assess the influence of ocean warming. Similarly, changes in the flow speeds of mountain glaciers can provide insights into atmospheric changes. By quantifying glacier velocities, researchers can gain a better understanding of whether glacial changes are primarily driven by oceanic or atmospheric conditions.

Read more about this study here:

<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/sensing-our-planet/a-glacial-pace>

Chile Glaciers

NASA JPL's L-band airborne radar (UAVSAR) collected imagery across different glaciers in the Andes in March 2013 and April 2014. The SAR interferograms showed motion on the

centimeter scale for glaciers in the Northern, Central, and Southern Andes. Glaciers in the Central Andes had a diverse range of motion over 2 days, ranging from 4-8 centimeters at Glaciar San Francisco to 60 centimeters at Glaciar Universidad.

The repeating colors are like contours on a topographic map that measure the change in the distance between the glacier and the satellite/aircraft radar.

San Francisco Glacier

Left: Optical Imagery

Right: UAVSAR Interferogram from March 25-27, 2013

UAVSAR product page: https://uavsar.jpl.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/product.pl?jobName=ChiGla_09200_13046-002_13048-013_0002d_s01_L090_01#data

Universidad Glacier

Left: Optical Imagery

Right: Interferogram from April 24-26, 2014

2 day motion in excess of 60 centimeters

UAVSAR product page: https://uavsar.jpl.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/product.pl?jobName=ChiGla_09300_14048-005_14051-020_0002d_s01_L090_01

Iceland Glaciers

Minchew et. al 2015 conducted research on two glaciers called Hofsjökull and Langjökull in Iceland. With L-band airborne SAR data, they used InSAR to collect data about the movement of the ice in these glaciers. Overall, the study used data and models to understand how the ice in these glaciers is moving and to infer the presence of slipping at the base of the glaciers, which is an important factor in studying glacier behavior and dynamics.

In the figure below the upper left (a) shows the horizontal movement of the ice in Hofsjökull. The arrows in the figure indicate the direction in which the ice is flowing, and the color map represents the speed of the horizontal movement. Reds and yellows indicate higher speeds.

In the figure's upper right (b), a model assumes the ice flows like a thick fluid without any slipping at the base. The color map shows the speed of this theoretical viscous flow, and the arrows indicate the gradient (slope) of the ice surface. The difference between the estimated speed of the viscous flow and the actual measured speed of the ice in the outlet glaciers suggests that there is slipping occurring at the base of the glacier. The black

Source: Minchew et. al 2015, <https://doi.org/10.3189/2015JogG14J023>

contours in the figure represent certain features, and the tan-colored areas surrounding the glacier show the elevation of the ground. In the figure, (c) and (d) show the same information for the Langjökull glacier.

It should be noted that the authors utilize airborne radar data from different flight track directions, which won't be available with NISAR.

Technology

Why SAR?

NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR) is an upcoming radar instrument collecting data in the L-band wavelength (23.8 cm), which will provide high-resolution, near-global, and continual mapping of Earth's natural resources and hazards. Explore the NISAR Sample Data Product Suite, or planned NISAR data products and their product specifications, here:

<https://nisar.jpl.nasa.gov/data/sample-data/>

Polar or high-elevation regions with glaciers can often have cloud cover, but unlike optical imagery, radar can penetrate the clouds and still map the glaciers below. Compared with optical data, SAR can penetrate through a glacier's ice to map velocities at different depths of the glacier. InSAR's large spatial coverage also has advantages over ground-based methods like GPS, which are limited to velocity tracking at specific points on the glacier.

With repeat-pass InSAR, researchers can monitor changes in glacier velocities over time, which helps inform glacier dynamics and the response of glaciers to various factors such as climate change. It provides valuable information for studying glacier behavior, identifying areas of fast flow or slow movement, and detecting potential hazards related to

glacial retreat or ice mass loss.

Interferometric SAR (InSAR)

Repeat-pass interferometric synthetic aperture radar (InSAR) is a remote sensing technique that uses radar signals to measure the movement of Earth's surface. In the context of glaciers, it allows for the monitoring and mapping of glacier surface velocities.

Radar sensors emit microwave pulses and measure the reflected signal. The signal has an amplitude and a phase. Amplitude is the strength of the reflected signal determined by the signal's interaction with surface properties on the ground. The phase is a specific point on the signal's wavelength cycle. The phase can be used to determine the distance from the radar sensor to the ground.

A technique called Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar or InSAR uses differences in reflected signal between two or more radar images to map surface changes down to the centimeter level. In addition to glacial motion, InSAR can be used to map surface deformation such as from land subsidence, earthquakes, and volcanic eruptions.

NISAR will use Repeat-Pass InSAR where observations are collected from the same location in space but at different times. When the ground moves between acquisitions, the distance changes between the ground and the radar, and a different fraction of the wavelength cycle, or phase shift, is reflected back to the radar.

An interferogram is generated by "interfering" or differencing phase values from two or more radar images to map ground displacement relative to the sensor. Using known radar wavelengths, interferograms detect change down to fractions of a wavelength or phase, which can then be converted to centimeters.

Interferograms are often depicted with a repeating color scale that shows the magnitude of the displacement. The direction of the displacement is indicated by the sequence of "fringes" or color progressions that repeat more frequently towards the center of the subsiding or uplifting areas. Each fringe cycle represents a certain range of change and the number of fringe cycles can be counted to determine displacement in centimeters. This USGS webpage details how to interpret interferograms: <https://www.usgs.gov/centers/land-subsidence-in-california/science/interferometric-synthetic-aperture-radar-insar>

Sensors with longer wavelengths like NISAR will also provide better estimates of glacier movement as the signal can penetrate deep into the glacier's surface and maintains better correlation when images are collected at different times. NISAR will collect data in the L-Band wavelength, or 23.8 cm. Check out NISAR's webpage on interferometry for more information: <https://nisar.jpl.nasa.gov/mission/get-to-know-sar/interferometry/>

References and Further Reading

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